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Povidone-iodine in wound healing and prevention of wound infections

Maksym K. Gmur¹, Tomasz M. Karpiński^{2*}

¹ Student Scientific Club of Medical Microbiology, Chair and Department of Medical Microbiology, Poznań University of Medical Sciences, Wieniawskiego 3, 61-712, Poznań, Poland

² Chair and Department of Medical Microbiology, Poznań University of Medical Sciences, Wieniawskiego 3, 61-712, Poznań, Poland

*Correspondence: E-mail: maksymgmur@gmail.com; tkarpin@ump.edu.pl

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ABSTRACT: The wound infections caused by bacteria and fungi are a significant problem in healthcare. Therefore, an effective treatment and prevention seems to be essential. Povidone-iodine is one of the commercial antimicrobial agents used for skin disinfection, in surgery and for local anti-infective treatment. The broad activity spectrum of this compound includes numerous species of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, mycobacteria, fungi, protozoa and viruses. Povidone-iodine is recommended for acute wounds as well as lacerations, bruises and deep wounds due to its good tissue penetration.

Keywords: Povidone-iodine; PVP-I; Antiseptic; Antimicrobial; Wound infection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bacteria are a part of the physiologic skin and mucous membranes flora and in that way wounds [1]. Additionally, non-pathogenic or potentially pathogenic microorganisms of transient flora reside the skin and mucous membranes for hours to weeks [2]. Exceeding the critical threshold of 10^5 bacteria (critical colonization) may cause an infection. Additionally, antibiotic-resistant strains can significantly impede wound healing [1].

Most chronic wounds comprise more than one bacterial species. Among them *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Corynebacterium spp.*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Serratia spp.*, *Fingoldia magna*, *Propionibacterium acnes*, *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Prevotella spp.*, and *Bacteroides fragilis* are the most often. An increase in surgical site infections (SSIs) correlated with methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) and vancomycin-resistant *S. aureus* were observed. Infections caused by fungi, such as *Candida albicans* and *C. glabrata* are also a significant problem. Moreover, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* are capable to form biofilms that contribute to antibiotic resistance [2-4].

To reduce the risk of infection, antiseptic agents are used. Antiseptics are naturally occurring or synthetic organic substances intended for local, topical use, that destroy or inhibit the growth of

microorganisms on skin, mucous membranes or damaged tissue [4]. One of the commercial antimicrobial agent is the polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine (povidone-iodine, PVP-I).

PVP-I was introduced in 1956 [5] and its routinely used as a preparation for skin disinfection w połączeniu z alkoholem ,oraz w śródoperacyjnie jako roztwór wodny w rozcieńczeniach in combination with alcohol and intraoperatively as a dilute solution. Its efficacy against wide variety of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, fungi, protozoa, viruses, good tolerability and lack of resistance suggests the correctness of use PVP-I in wound healing and infection prevention [6-9].

2. CHEMICAL ASPECTS

Povidone-iodine is a yellowish-brown chemical complex of 1-ethenylpyrrolidin-2-one and molecular iodine with a slight characteristic odor. The iodine content is from 9.0 to 12.0% (calculated on a dry basis). The substance has a molecular formula $C_6H_9I_2NO$ and a molecular weight 364.95 g/mol [10]. Figure 1 shows the chemical structure of the compound.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of povidone-iodine.

The solubility of PVP-I at water and alcohol is good and it is practically insoluble in acetone, chloroform, light petroleum or carbon tetrachloride. There are available different concentrations of PVP-I used depending on the purpose: as a 10%, 7.5%, 5%, 1.28%, 1% and also 0.45% formulation (as a throat spray) [10, 11]. The 10% commercial formulation is composed of 90% water, 8.5% povidone and 1% iodine and iodide [12, 13].

Mixing povidone and iodine indicates a chemical reaction. It is considered that iodine is complexed by polyvinylpyrrolidone and iodide through a hydrogen bond between two pyrroles. As a result, povidone-iodine exists with a small amount of free iodine. It has been documented that exposure to organic substances like whole blood, pus or fat reduces a bactericidal activity of PVP-I. It is most likely caused by iodine complexing and chemical reactions, such as the reduction to iodide. Moreover, approximately 46 to 59 mg of iodine is bound by one gram of hemoglobin [6]. In addition, it is worth remembering that in chronic wounds, iodine compounds should not be combined with silver-containing dressings, also due to the precipitation of iodides [4].

3. MODE OF ACTION

The microbicidal activity of PVP-I is based on release the free iodine to the solution from the PVP-I complex. PVP provides iodine to cells membranes, but itself has no biocidal properties. There has been demonstrated the paradoxical behavior of substance; in contrast to other iodine preparations, the content of free iodine primitively increases with the increasing dilution, reaching a maximum value at about 0.1% formulation and decreasing on further dilution [14]. This translates into antimicrobial activity of compound [7].

The iodine effects on amino, thiol and phenolic hydroxyl groups of amino acids and nucleotides in biological structures. Additionally, iodine reacts with the double bonds of unsaturated fatty acids in the cell wall and membranes of organelles [15]. This mode of action leads to disruption of pathogens metabolic pathways and irreversible damage of the cell membranes structural components. PVP-I also inhibits the production and secrete of bacterial exotoxins [3, 11, 16].

The virucidal mechanism of action is based on the inhibition of essential viral enzymes. The inactivation of neuraminidase prevents viral release from the host cell, making a further spread of the virus to uninfected cells impossible. Haemagglutinin is also inhibited by iodophor and attachment to host cell receptor is blocked [17].

4. ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

PVP-I has a broad spectrum of antimicrobial activity even after a short time of exposition [7]. It demonstrates efficacy against Gram-positive, Gram-negative, various spore-forming bacteria (*Clostridium* spp., *Bacillus* spp.), mycobacteria and also enveloped and non-enveloped viruses [8, 18]. Equally inactivation of antibiotic sensitive and resistant staphylococci and enterococci, such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterococcus faecalis*, by PVP-I was demonstrated [19-22]. Also Gram-negative bacteria, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* presented sensitivity on PVP-I [17, 20, 23]. Minimal inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of PVP-I against some bacterial and fungal species are presented in Table 1.

Biofilms impede wound healing and increase resistance to antibiotics. Studies have shown the *in vitro* efficacious of PVP-I against *S. epidermidis*, *S. aureus* and *Candida albicans* growth, as well as the inhibition biofilm formation [8]. Moreover, the iodophor revealed fungicidal activity against *Candida auris* [24], *Aspergillus flavus* and *Cryptococcus neoformans* [6].

Table 1. MICs (minimal inhibitory concentrations) of PVP-I against bacterial and fungal species.

Species	MIC (µg/mL)	References
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	0.24-512	[3, 25, 26]
Methicillin-resistant <i>S. aureus</i> (MRSA)	7.81-5210	[9, 25, 27]
<i>S. epidermidis</i>	781-5000	[28, 29]
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	490-4688	[9, 27]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	4-1024	[25, 26, 30]
Carbapenem-resistant <i>E. coli</i> (CREC)	4-128	[30]
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	4-64	[30]
Carbapenem-resistant <i>K. pneumoniae</i> (CRKP)	8-128	[9, 30]
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	125-8330	[3, 27]
<i>Chlamydia trachomatis</i>	97-1562	[9, 31]
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	3130-4688	[9, 27]
<i>Candida albicans</i>	256-5000	[25, 32, 33]
<i>C. glabrata</i>	10-5000	[32, 33]
<i>Cryptococcus sp.</i>	2500	[32]

Viruses and chlamydia play a meaningful role in infections. PVP solutions indicate high effective against *Herpes simplex* virus and excellent efficacy against the enveloped influenza A virus. Adenovirus type 8 proved to be sensitive to PVP-I, although, contrary to *Herpes simplex*, a longer time of exposure was necessary to inactivation. Enteroviruses and *Coxsackievirus* were resistant to povidone-iodine [7, 17].

5. APPLICATION

PVP-I has a wide range of applications. In 2014, European Chemicals Agency approved PVP-I as an existing active substance for use in biocidal products for types 1, 3, 4, and 22 (human hygiene, veterinary hygiene, food and feed area, and embalming and taxidermist fluids) [9]. Efficacy of wound infection treatment, prophylactic intraoperative wound irrigation, hand wash preparations, skin disinfection and topical antiseptic has been shown [13, 34-37]. Povidone-iodine is available in a pre- and postoperative skin disinfection [38, 39].

PVP-I as an antiseptic formulation is the first choice for stab, bite and gunshot wounds [3]. In difficult-to-heal wounds (including chronic wounds), it is not recommended due to its cytotoxicity, limitations of use, and the incompatibility between PVP-I and the silver-based dressings [40]. It is also useful in the care of surgical wounds, and in wounds such as the diabetic foot, as it can be used to rinse deep wounds with lack drainage [41-43]. The use of PVP-I as a vaginal antiseptic has also been demonstrated. Presurgical vaginal irrigation with PVP-I significantly reduces the risk of post-cesarean endometritis, wound infections and pyrexia in patients who underwent cesarean delivery [44, 45].

Some studies indicate that PVP-I formulations are effective in eradication pathogenic cultures of the external auditory canal after tympanoplasty [46], in intraocular injection, ophthalmic surgery, also as a cataract surgery [12], in treating the corneal ulcers [47] or preventing post-cystoscopy urinary tract infection (UTI) [48]. Moreover, PVP-I is used for mucosal antiseptics, in oral surgery and dental conditions [11]. Studies present the positive effects of PVP-I gargles/mouthwashes against *Bordetella pertussis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* strains [18, 49].

However, an equally important factor conditioning the proper healing process is the low cytotoxicity of the antiseptic. The Biocompatibility Index (BI) may be helpful in choosing the right preparation (Table 2).

Table 2. Biocompatibility index as a quotient of IC₅₀ for L929 cells and the required MIC for a reduction factor of $\geq 3 \log_{10}$ [40].

Compound	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
Octenidine	1,7	2,1
PHMB	1,5	1,4
PVP-I (aqueous solution, referring on I ₂)	0,9	1,0
Chlorhexidine	0,7	0,7
Triclosan	0,2	0,5
Ag-protein (referring on Ag ⁺)	0,2	0,1
Ag(I)-sulfadiazine and silver nitrate	not measurable	

The BI value >1 indicates that a given product has a broad spectrum against microorganisms and a low level of cytotoxicity against fibroblasts or keratinocytes, and therefore its use does not adversely affect the healing process. It is also important that the antiseptic preparation has a high degree of penetration through

biofilm structures, does not induce resistance build-up, and does not cause incompatibility with other substances contained in dressings and has the ability to prolonged operation (residua effect). Currently, in clinical practice, the most frequently chosen antiseptics for the prevention and treatment of chronic wounds are octenidine and iodine-containing agents (such as iodine povidone) [4, 40, 50].

Sometimes, sensitizations against PVP-I cross-reacts to iodinated contrast media. However, these can be detected by a simple skin test. In addition, PVP-I allergies are relatively rare [8]. Hypersensitivity to the povidone-iodine, hyperthyroidism, toxic nodular goiter, herpes dermatitis syndrome, radioactive iodine therapy and peritoneal lavage are contraindications to povidone-iodine usage. Application during pregnancy and breastfeeding, as well as in patients under 12 years old is not recommended [3, 51].

6. CONCLUSION

Povidone-iodine is a relatively inexpensive antimicrobial agent characterized by a broad spectrum of activity, efficacy against biofilms and no resistance. Additionally, rapid action and good tolerability confirm the appropriateness of using PVP-I formulations in the clinical treatment of surgical wounds and the prevention of infections. PVP-I may help reduce the wound healing period and shorten the hospitalization as well as reduce treatment costs.

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